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CLIMATE-NATURE SYNERGIES: from local to global

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1. INTRODUCTION TO THE CLIMATE-NATURE SYNERGIES AGENDA

1.1 What is the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda and why does it matter?

Climate change and biodiversity loss represent two of the greatest global challenges of our time. The world is in a state of climate emergency, with 2024 marking the first year in which the global average temperature rose more than 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.¹ The effects have intensified year after year, with alarming extreme events becoming increasingly frequent. Six of the nine planetary boundaries have already been crossed, showing that Earth's life support systems are operating beyond their safe levels.²

Although distinct, both crises are deeply interconnected phenomena with reciprocal impacts. Environmental degradation undermines ecosystems' ability to regulate climate, while global warming accelerates habitat destruction and species loss.

Tropical basins such as the Amazon Basin are emblematic of this interconnection.³ Home to over 10% of the world's terrestrial biodiversity and 10% of all known fish species,⁴ the Amazon's rich biodiversity plays a vital role in regulating the global climate, yet it is increasingly threatened by deforestation, forest degradation, and the direct effects of climate change. The Amazon is also a deeply unequal region, marked by multiple overlapping insecurities – national, public, human, food, and legal – which add layers of complexity to global efforts to safeguard the forest and its peoples.⁵

The consequences of the dual climate and biodiversity crisis in the Amazon are not limited to the local level; they affect vulnerable populations worldwide, as well as water, food, and climate security across the Basin countries and beyond.

The symbiotic relationship between the climate and biodiversity crises in the Amazon and beyond show that, although they are often addressed in a fragmented way in the domestic and multilateral political-institutional scenario, both are in fact inseparable in their impacts and solutions. In other words, integrated, coordinated, and systemic responses are needed to address both crises.

It is in this context that the so-called Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda emerges: an effort to promote greater coherence between actions to reverse the climate crisis and those to protect biodiversity, thereby safeguarding the [ecological integrity](#) of ecosystems by [maximizing benefits and minimizing trade-offs](#) (see Glossary). This endeavor is essentially multilevel and multidimensional, aiming to protect people, climate, and nature at different scales — from local to global.

By characterizing the “Synergies Agenda” as an effort, we make it clear that it is not a formalized, institutionalized, or agreed-upon agenda: neither at the multilateral level nor at the regional or national level, including in contexts such as the Amazon Basin and Brazil. What we observe instead is an agenda building process that is still unfolding, through experimentation and technical-political debate, aimed at strengthening “synergistic” multilateral, regional, and national instruments and initiatives.

In this context, the Synergies Agenda calls, first and foremost, for greater dialogue and alignment between international legal instruments, especially between the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Convention on Biological Diversity (UNFCCC and CBD), and between these two and the three [Rio Conventions](#) (see Glossary), as well as with other international environmental agreements on desertification, oceans, and pollution, and with other initiatives such as the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Yet more than promoting dialogue between conventions, the Synergies Agenda is above all an implementation agenda: it seeks to strengthen existing public policy and economic instruments in different countries while fostering the creation of new national, regional, and international mechanisms that incorporate both biodiversity conservation and climate mitigation and adaptation into their mandates and objectives.

In **Climate-Nature Synergies: From Local to Global**, the Igarapé Institute uses the case of Brazil and the Amazon Basin as starting points to explore the opportunities and challenges of fostering dialogue between the climate and nature agendas, highlighting the importance of promoting synergies across multiple levels: national, regional, and global. This study identifies ongoing programs and policies that showcase synergistic approaches between climate and nature in Brazil and other Amazonian countries, as well as multilateral initiatives that encourage greater dialogue and alignment between these agendas within the framework of the Rio Conventions and their instruments. We focus specifically on the Climate and Biodiversity Conventions, while also referencing, whenever possible, other international environmental and non-environmental political and diplomatic instruments and processes at the United Nations (UN) and other multilateral spaces

Through the systematization of ongoing policies, instruments, and initiatives, the sections in this study highlight actions in all three levels to promote climate-nature

synergies. These include: greater alignment between national climate and biodiversity plans; prioritization of synergistic, high integrity financial solutions; promotion of public policy instruments that deliver multiple benefits and can be scaled; and reforms in international climate governance. By presenting an overview of ongoing actions, we underscore synergistic approaches already being considered and tested in countries such as Brazil, across the Amazon Basin, and within several multilateral institutions and processes.

In listing these ongoing actions, we stress the contribution of the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda to efforts aimed at strengthening global environmental and climate governance, advancing the implementation of existing international commitments. We also show how current initiatives can leverage the development of new technical, political, and financial partnerships, reinforcing solutions in Brazil and the Amazon Basin and promoting the exchange of experiences among Amazonian countries, as well as between them and other tropical basins, in a context of growing mobilization around tropical forest conservation.

1.2 The Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda and COP30 in Brazil and the Amazon: How to move forward?

Given the growing prominence of the Climate–Nature Synergies debate in multilateral forums, as well as in public policy instruments and national and regional initiatives in Brazil and across the Amazon Basin, 2025 presents key opportunities to further consolidate and institutionalize this agenda at multiple levels.

While experimentation and innovation are underway at the national level in countries such as Brazil, the coming years will be decisive in ensuring continuity, robustness, and scaling of these actions. It will also be essential to invest in strengthening dialogue and cooperation at the regional level in the Amazon Basin and across tropical basins to foster the exchange of policies and experiences, and to build regional and global initiatives that promote synergies in ecosystems critical to the climate and biodiversity agendas.

At the international level, a series of proposals have gained momentum in recent years across different multilateral forums to reinforce integrated global governance between the climate and biodiversity agendas. Such strengthening is vital to enable multilateral processes to promote greater policy coherence, refine institutional mechanisms, and ensure that integrated approaches are translated into global actions for climate mitigation, adaptation, and biodiversity conservation.

Among the main challenges today are the lack of clear and effective multilateral mechanisms to align the climate and biodiversity agendas, and the inadequacy of existing financial and technical cooperation instruments to

support the further implementation of the Rio Conventions, as well as to strengthen public policies and synergistic investments for climate and nature.

With COP30 approaching in November 2025, Brazil has an opportunity to advance policy coherence efforts within the UNFCCC framework. The Brazilian Presidency has emphasized the importance of strengthening the implementation agenda of the Climate COPs, and the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda is a strong ally in this effort, offering both a tangible outcome and a potential legacy for the COP in Belém.

In the context of growing efforts to strengthen and reform global governance, advancing the synergies agenda also represents a step toward feasible reforms in the current geopolitical scenario. Connecting multilateral efforts for the climate and nature agendas contributes not only to improving global environmental and climate governance, by reducing fragmentation and optimizing available resources, but also to reforming the international financial architecture, enhancing high-integrity international financing that delivers co-benefits for the climate, nature, and people.

This study is organized into four sections: Introduction to the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda; Synergies at the National Level: Brazil; Synergies at the Regional Level: Amazon Basin; and Synergies at the Global Level: Multilateral Spaces.

GLOSSARY

Biodiversity and Nature

Both terms are used in the international debate on synergies. While international law generally addresses the issue under the umbrella of biodiversity, numerous initiatives frame it through a “climate and nature” perspective. Domestically, in countries such as Brazil, “biodiversity” is a formally established term in national legislation, defined and regulated by frameworks such as the National Biodiversity Policy ⁶ and Law n^o 9.985/2000.⁷ By contrast, the term “nature” lacks a consolidated legal definition.

Integration, Alignment, and Synergies

The term “synergies” has been the most frequently used in international debates and in efforts to advance dialogue, alignment, connections, and compatibility between climate and nature agendas. Although terms such as “integration” are common in the field of public policy and global governance,⁸ the preference for “synergies” in this case reflects a dual concern. On the one hand, it acknowledges the need to reduce fragmentation and competition between international regimes and agendas, and to promote “mutual gains” and “co-benefits” (see below). On the other hand, it incorporates the legal, political, and diplomatic concerns of many countries with ensuring respect for the authority and distinctions of the various agreements and their mandates, as well as the commitments made by countries in each of them.

Co-benefits and Trade-offs

Overlap and competition between agendas, regimes, and instruments are common phenomena in both public policy and international relations. Efforts to bring climate and nature agendas closer together therefore seek to “maximize co-benefits and minimize trade-offs.” For example, poorly planned climate mitigation measures — such as monocultures for carbon sequestration or the construction of renewable energy parks in areas of high biological importance — can harm biodiversity. By contrast, nature-based solutions, such as ecosystem restoration and sustainable forest management, illustrate a viable path for integrating climate change mitigation with biodiversity conservation in an effective and balanced way.⁹

Ecosystem Integrity or Ecological Integrity

Ecosystem Integrity, also known as Ecological Integrity, refers to the capacity of an ecosystem to maintain its composition, structure, functioning, and self-organization over time within a natural range of variability at landscape scales. It is a scientific concept established for several decades and referenced in official documents and national and international regulations, including the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (1992), the Paris Agreement, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), and IPCC reports. It is a fundamental concept for assessing the “risk of loss” of carbon stocks, and, therefore, an important tool for climate mitigation actions, while maximizing synergies with biodiversity and the provision of essential ecosystem services.¹⁰

Natural Climate Solutions (NCS) and Nature-based Solutions (NbS)

Natural climate solutions result from the human management of ecosystems and focus specifically on mitigating climate change. Nature-based solutions, by contrast, encompass actions that address broader social challenges through the protection, sustainable management, and restoration of ecosystems, delivering benefits for both biodiversity and human well-being. It is therefore not uncommon for the two to overlap.¹¹

Rio Conventions

The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), and the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) are “sister conventions” that emerged from the Earth Summit held in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 (also known as Rio-92 or Eco-92). These three Rio Conventions stemmed from shared concerns about environmental and development challenges, with sustainable development as their central focus. Given their complementary nature, UN Member States and the UN Secretariat have sought to expand dialogue and foster joint work among them, recognizing the growing severity of challenges related to climate change, desertification, and biodiversity loss, and pursuing increasingly integrated solutions.¹²

2. CLIMATE-NATURE SYNERGIES AT THE NATIONAL LEVEL: BRAZIL

This section examines the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda at the national level through the Brazilian case. It highlights the challenges of decarbonization in Brazil and the potential of nature-based solutions for achieving the country's NDC, showing how climate-nature synergies are already embedded in Brazil's public policies and climate diplomacy. By mapping existing instruments and initiatives, even if at different stages of maturity, it identifies opportunities to catalyze synergies between climate and nature agendas, demonstrating in practice how these connections can be advanced at the national level.

2.1 Climate-Nature Synergies and the Ecological Transition in Brazil

Brazil is home to the world's richest biodiversity. This extraordinary variety of life — representing more than 20% of all known species on Earth¹³ — places the country at the forefront of the 17 megadiverse countries.¹⁴ Within this scenario, the Brazilian Amazon plays a central role. Covering about 60% of its area within Brazil's national territory, it is the largest tropical forest in the world and harbors roughly 10% of global biodiversity.¹⁵ Within this scenario, the Brazilian Amazon plays a central role. Covering about 60% of its area within Brazil's national territory, it is the largest tropical forest in the world and harbors roughly 10% of global biodiversity solutions nationally and regionally, through cooperation with neighboring Amazonian countries, while also serving as a model for other regions of the world.

Brazil is currently the sixth largest emitter of greenhouse gases (GHG), accounting for 3.1% of global emissions in 2023.¹⁶ Unlike most other major emitters, whose emissions stem mainly from the energy, transport, and industrial sectors, in Brazil the primary source is linked to land use change — driven by deforestation and degradation caused by forest fires — as well as by agriculture and livestock. Together, these activities account for approximately 75% of national emissions.¹⁷

This Brazilian peculiarity — also observed, albeit to a lesser extent, in other Amazonian countries and in forest-rich nations such as Indonesia — requires embedding climate-nature synergies at the core of mitigation initiatives and strategies for decarbonization and ecological transformation. Brazil is currently structuring its path toward ecological transition and carbon neutrality (net zero) around three main pillars: natural climate solutions, especially positive changes in land use and forest management; changes in the energy matrix; and nature-based solutions. The first pillar — NCS focused on positive changes in land use¹⁸ — is especially strategic for Brazil. Globally, it is estimated that these solutions could deliver between 20% and 50% of the emissions reduction needed by 2030, equivalent to 5 to 12 gigatons of CO₂ equivalent (CO₂-eq).¹⁹

Brazil and Indonesia lead the world in potential for low-cost NCS, with Brazil accounting for approximately 15% of this potential — the highest share among countries, followed by Indonesia.²⁰ This potential stems from the wide availability of areas for forest restoration, sustainable agricultural practices, and ecosystem conservation, all of which can contribute significantly to carbon removal and reduction. Recent modeling for Brazil indicates

that forest protection is the main mitigation measure in the short term, responsible for more than 90% of emissions reductions by 2030. Over the long term, restoration gains prominence, contributing up to 18% of the total mitigation potential, although its impacts unfold more slowly, as decades are needed to rebuild carbon stocks.²¹

In addition, land use change and agriculture represent the most economically viable pathways for decarbonization in Brazil, with costs below USD 20 per metric ton of CO₂ equivalent.²² In practice, investments in agricultural decarbonization, through regenerative practices, integrated systems, bio-inputs, and the recovery of degraded pastures, among others, can generate net benefits.²³ Estimates suggest that for every dollar invested in reducing emissions from livestock, there is a potential return of USD 2 in productivity gains.²⁴

Beyond natural climate solutions, Brazil also has strategic assets that can contribute economically and efficiently to the country's ecological transition and to global emissions reductions, including its vast potential for renewable energy. The renewable energy and bioenergy market in the country is projected to reach USD 90 billion by 2040.²⁵ Although the country's energy matrix has remained predominantly clean for decades, the energy transition and progress toward decarbonization of the power sector are already being driven by regulatory milestones such as the Legal Framework for Microgeneration and Distributed Mini-generation²⁶ the Fuel of the Future bill,²⁷ Offshore Wind Power²⁸ and Low Carbon Hydrogen²⁹ framework. These initiatives provide legal certainty for investors and encourage the expansion of biofuels and new clean energy sources, including in more remote locations, many of them within the Legal Amazon.³⁰

The transition to a low-carbon economy also opens up strategic opportunities for Brazil in sectors such as attracting data centers, which demand clean and stable energy, and in the sustainable development of critical minerals

essential for energy storage technologies, electric vehicles, and renewable energy. Brazil holds significant reserves of these minerals, including niobium, graphite, nickel, and lithium, and has around 50 projects underway dedicated to the exploration of critical minerals useful for the energy transition.³¹ This advantage could position the country as a key player in the global market for minerals vital for decarbonization.³²

Studies suggest that by seizing these opportunities, Brazil could add up to USD 100 billion to its GDP by 2030.³³ However, both biofuels and the race for critical minerals come with trade-offs, posing risks and potential negative socio-environmental impacts, such as increased pressure on sensitive ecosystems, accelerated environmental degradation, and threats to food production and food security. In addition, disputes over benefit sharing in the case of critical minerals may exacerbate conflicts, including in Indigenous territories and traditional communities in the Amazon that are already heavily affected by mining. The absence of clear regulations and effective mechanisms for traceability and integrity assurance further increases the risk of overlap between legal and illegal mining, amplifying socio-environmental vulnerabilities and undermining governance of the sector.³⁴

Finally, alongside natural climate solutions and the energy transition, Brazil also stands out in the use of NbS — approaches that not only remove carbon but also generate socio-environmental co-benefits for the population. The country holds about 20% of the world's total NbS³⁵ potential. One example is the possibility of reconciling food, energy, and environmental objectives by converting 61 to 85 million hectares of degraded pasture into native forests, planted energy forests, and sustainable agricultural practices.³⁶ According to the Brazilian Restoration and Reforestation Observatory (BRRO), in 2024 more than 150,000 hectares were already under restoration in Brazil, representing a 90% increase over 2021 levels.³⁷

To fully realize this potential, the country will need to invest in political and regulatory frameworks and economic instruments capable of balancing the imperatives of decarbonization with socio-environmental protection. By doing so, Brazil can position itself as a leader in global decarbonization, offering sustainable and NbS to the world. Its unique position — home to the planet's greatest biodiversity while also ranking among the largest GHG emitters — gives the country a strategic role in global biodiversity and climate conferences, reinforcing its longstanding influence in international negotiations on these agendas and its current role in promoting synergies between climate and nature in an integrated, effective, and socially just manner.

2.2 Climate-Nature Synergies in Brazil's public policies and climate diplomacy

Since the 1980s and 1990s, Brazil has played a central role in shaping the international environmental and climate agenda. This leadership has traditionally sought to reconcile environmental protection with the right to development, while also strengthening the autonomy and sovereignty of developing countries in managing their natural resources and ecosystems, including, critically, the Amazon

Brazil's influence is evident across multilateral negotiation processes. The country was instrumental in creating and promoting the concept of sustainable development and the principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDR), as well as in implementing the mechanism for Reducing Emissions from Deforestation and Forest Degradation (REDD+) and in shaping the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). From the Rio-92 and Rio+20 Conferences to the adoption of the 2030 Agenda, Brazil's

leadership has been consistent, establishing the country as both a bridge builder and a consensus builder.³⁸

In recent years, especially since 2023, Brazil has intensified its role as a coordinator of developing countries interests in tropical forest governance. This includes strengthening cooperation among Amazonian countries through the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) and engaging in extra-regional initiatives such as the United for Our Forests Group and the Tropical Forest Forever Facility (TFFF)³⁹ — a forest conservation financing mechanism that Brazil intends to officially launch at COP30 in Belém in November 2025.

In 2024, Brazil played an important role at COP16 on Biodiversity, alongside host country Colombia, by facilitating a proposal to establish a Joint Work Program between the Rio Conventions. The proposal is still pending approval but represents progress toward formalizing a more synergistic dialogue among the Conventions (see Section 4). Brazil views the synergies agenda as a tool for implementing the Conventions, especially at the national and local levels, in line with national circumstances and priorities for promoting sustainable developments.⁴⁰

In this context, and given that the Brazilian Presidency of COP30 has prioritized the implementation of commitments previously negotiated under the Climate Convention, the synergies agenda acquires strategic relevance. It enables the articulation of feasible reforms in environmental and climate governance and fosters discussions on climate finance, including in relation to forest conservation.

At the domestic level, Brazil is experiencing a moment of significant political innovation in the synergies agenda, especially at the interface with the forest-related policies. Within the public sector, both in discourse and in policy, there is a growing recognition of the need to promote synergies between actions targeting

climate change agendas and those aimed at preserving and enhancing ecosystem services. In a recent speech at the opening of the BRICS Environment Ministers' meeting in April 2025, Brazilian Minister Marina Silva said that it is “essential to move forward simultaneously with concrete actions that increase climate financing — from the USD 300 billion promised to at least USD 1.3 trillion annually“ and, to this end, to “strengthen innovative financing mechanisms,“ such as TFFF, “which seeks to ensure continuous resources for the protection of nature and the enhancement of ecosystem services in tropical forests.”⁴¹

Ambassador André Corrêa do Lago, then Secretary of Climate, Energy, and Environment at the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and now President-designate of COP30, also highlighted during COP16 of the CBD in Colombia in 2024 that “the Conventions reflect the advancement of scientific knowledge, reinforcing the urgent need to integrate the climate change and biodiversity agendas.”⁴²

In parallel, since 2023, the federal government has reinforced numerous public policy instruments designed to promote and enable synergistic climate-nature approaches. In addition to submitting Brazil's new Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) to the UNFCCC in 2024, the Ministry of the Environment and Climate Change (MMA, in Portuguese) is finalizing two key documents for this agenda: the revised National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP), to be submitted to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), which contains more ambitious targets aligned with the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KM-GBF), and the Climate Plan (Plano Clima, in Portuguese), the country's primary instrument for intersectoral coordination of climate policy, which will be implemented through sectoral adaptation and mitigation plans.

Currently in its final stages of preparation under the Interministerial Committee on Climate Change (CIM, in Portuguese), the Climate Plan is expected to be launched before COP30.

Designed as an umbrella plan, the document spans three cycles of targets established in the NDCs (2025, 2030, and 2035), and informs the most recent update presented at COP29 in 2024. The Climate Plan will include seven sectoral mitigation plans and 16 adaptation plans, all with direct or indirect interfaces with the broader biodiversity and nature agenda. More specifically, the main entry points for strengthening integration between national agendas — and thereby aligning the NDC, the NBSAP, and national adaptation plans — include sectoral mitigation plans for agriculture and livestock, land use and forests, as well as adaptation plans focused on biodiversity, food and nutritional security, family farming, Indigenous peoples, and traditional communities, among others.

With regard to the Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan, although the deadline for its submission to the CBD has been set for 2024, the most up-to-date version, replacing the previous 2017 plan, is expected to be published in the second half of 2025.⁴³ Officially announced in June 2025, the new Brazilian NBSAP is under the responsibility of the National Biodiversity Commission (Conabio, in Portuguese), a body created to promote the implementation of Brazil's commitments under the CBD. Its content has been developed through internal consultations with the federal government and public consultations with society.

In February 2025, Resolution No. 9 was published, recommending the adoption of National Biodiversity Goals for the 2025–2030 period and their implementation by the Federal Government. These goals are to be incorporated into the new NBSAP and can be implemented with the voluntary cooperation of states, the Federal District, municipalities, civil society, and the private sector. Among the goals with the greatest potential for synergy with the climate agenda are Target 1B (zero deforestation), 2 (ecosystem restoration), 3 (conservation and management), 8 (impacts of climate change), 9 (sustainable use and

bioeconomy), 10A (sustainable productive activities), 12 (green and blue urban infrastructure), 14 (integration into public policies), 15 (sustainable business activities), and 16 (consumption and waste).

These targets provide strategic opportunities for coordination with the NDCs, national adaptation plans, and instruments such as the National Policy for the Recovery of Native Vegetation (Proveg, in Portuguese) and the National Plan for the Recovery of Native Vegetation (Planaveg, in Portuguese), discussed below, thereby strengthening integration between the biodiversity and climate agendas.⁴⁴

Brazil's current NDC, which aims to reduce national emissions by 59%–67% by 2035 compared to 2005 levels, also incorporates a series of actions with strong synergies across the biodiversity, land use, and forest agendas, thereby strengthening co-benefits between climate mitigation and environmental conservation. Among the programs and policies, notable examples include: conservation actions in Conservation Units and Indigenous Lands; conservation and restoration of marine and coastal biomes; measures to tackle deforestation, such as the Action Plans for the Prevention and Control of Deforestation in the Amazon and the Cerrado (PPCDAm and PPCerrado, in Portuguese); the Amazon Protected Areas Program (Arpa, in Portuguese), and other actions linked to the implementation of the Forest Code.

Also noteworthy are actions to enhance and restore native vegetation, such as the Florestas+ Program Planaveg. Revised in 2023 for the 2025-2028 period, Planaveg aims to recover native vegetation on private and public lands, including protected areas, low-productivity rural areas, Conservation Units, Indigenous Lands, and other collective territories. The goal is to expand and strengthen public policies, financial incentives, markets, good agricultural

practices, and other measures needed to restore at least 12 million hectares of native vegetation by December 31, 2030.⁴⁵

To this end, the MMA has worked in partnership with other government agencies to strengthen incentives and economic instruments that encourage investment in restoration, as well as integrated production systems compatible with the standing forest through the promotion of the socio-bioeconomy.⁴⁶ In addition to the National Bioeconomy Development Plan (PNDBio, in Portuguese), examples include initiatives in partnership with Brazil's National Development Bank (BNDES, in Portuguese), such as the Amazon Fund and the Restore the Amazon program, implemented in the Amazon Restoration Arc with BRL 50 million from the Amazon Fund and BRL 50 million from Petrobras for ecological and/or productive restoration projects.⁴⁷ In parallel, both BNDES and the Central Bank have advanced nature positive-related policies, for example by prohibiting the granting of rural credit to clients with active environmental embargoes.⁴⁸

On a parallel track, the Brazilian government is also strengthening regulations and creating market mechanisms for climate and nature. Beyond carbon markets, in November 2025 Brazil will issue its first batch of Environmental Reserve Quota (CRA, in Portuguese).⁴⁹ Established under Brazil's 2012 Forest Code, these quotas are a conservation tool designed to create state-level markets through which landowners can meet their legal obligations by purchasing quotas — or assets — to protect equivalent areas located on other properties.⁵⁰

In addition, a new set of specialized instruments for the socio-bioeconomy is being rolled out within the framework of consolidated agriculture and agrarian development programs such as the National Program for Strengthening Family Agriculture, the Safra Plan, and the Minimum Price Guarantee Policy (through lines such as Pronaf Floresta, RenovAgro Ambiental, and PGPMBio). Within the partnership with the

Ministry of Agrarian Development and Family Agriculture (MDA, in Portuguese), one example is the Productive Forests Program, which seeks to expand Brazil's capacity to produce healthy foods and socio-biodiversity products through Technical Assistance and Rural Extension (Ater, in Portuguese).⁵¹

The role of the State and public policies as drivers and catalysts of an economy compatible with standing forests — through regulation, training, and, above all, financing⁵² — is also reflected in cross-cutting initiatives led by the Ministry of Finance, such as the Ecological Transformation Plan, the EcolInvest Brasil, the Nature Investment Lab (NIL), and Brazil's Country Platform, known as the Platform for Climate Investment and Ecological Transformation (BIP). The latter includes a dedicated pillar on SbN and the bioeconomy, prioritizing sub-sectors such as sustainable fuels, native vegetation recovery, sustainable management of native vegetation, agricultural bio-inputs and green fertilizers, waste management, regenerative agriculture, and biotechnology. Through the BIP and pipeline initiatives such as the TFFF, Brazil aims to attract public and private investment to enable strategic projects, including those explicitly aligned with the climate and nature agendas.

Despite the political challenges in reaching consensus on major national plans and strategies, the number of initiatives underway shows concrete efforts to design more synergistic instruments. This panorama illustrates a scenario in which a wide range of public sector actors — extending well beyond traditional environmental agencies — together with the private sector, are fundamental to implementing actions that connect climate and nature. At the same time, the proliferation of these synergistic programs and instruments at the domestic level reinforces Brazil's increasingly active foreign policy on these issues, positioning COP30 as an opportunity to advance the synergies agenda within the Rio Conventions and to bolster Brazil's efforts to secure financing for tropical forests at the multilateral level.⁵³

Table 1 below provides a non-exhaustive overview of public policy instruments already in place (plans, programs, policies, actions, and funds) that illustrate the potential of a more integrated approach and its application already underway in Brazil. Although at different stages of maturity, these initiatives are important entry points for catalyzing synergies between climate and nature agendas, showing in practice how these connections can be achieved.

At the same time, the private and financial sectors have begun adopting innovative strategies to finance the socio-bioeconomy, NbS, and Payments for Environmental or Ecosystem Services (PES), such as carbon credits.⁵⁴ These initiatives are testing and refining business models that balance environmental preservation with economic value creation, demonstrating the transformative potential of nature-positive investments that integrate sustainable development and conservation. However, ensuring the integrity of these initiatives remains essential by mitigating risks such as corruption, money laundering, and greenwashing⁵⁵ through robust transparency, monitoring, and accountability mechanisms, so that the promised environmental and social benefits are effectively delivered.

Table 1. Instruments and initiatives that promote climate-nature synergies in Brazil

Instrument	Climate-Nature Synergies
NDC (2035)	Commits to reducing Brazil's emissions by 59%–67% by 2035 through synergistic actions across the biodiversity, land use, and forest agendas, strengthening co-benefits between climate mitigation and environmental conservation.
National Plan for the Recovery of Native Vegetation (Planaveg)	Expands and strengthens public policies, financial incentives, markets, good agricultural and cattle-ranching practices, and other measures needed to restore native vegetation, reducing emissions and enhancing biodiversity through more connected and resilient ecosystems.
Minimum Price Guarantee Policy for Socio-Biodiversity Products (PGPMBio)	Supports extractivist communities through subsidies based on a list of products with guaranteed minimum prices. By stabilizing prices for extractivists, it promotes ecosystem conservation, reduces deforestation, and increases the value of economic activities compatible with standing forests, while contributing to climate and biodiversity goals and securing income for traditional populations.
National Policy on Payment for Environmental Services (PNPSA)	Payment for Environmental Services (PES) are economic instruments that compensate rural producers, family farmers, traditional peoples, and settlers for maintaining, restoring, or improving ecosystems. The PNPSA was approved in 2021 (Law No. 14,119).
Action Plans for the Prevention and Control of Deforestation in the Amazon and the Cerrado (PPCDAm and PPCerrado)	The National Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Deforestation in the Legal Amazon in the Legal Amazon (PPCDAm) is currently in its 5th phase (2023–2027). The Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Deforestation and Fires in the Cerrado Biome (PPCerrado) is in its 4th phase (2023–2027). Despite the specificities of each biome, both plans share common goals: achieving zero deforestation by 2030; expanding concessions in public forests; strengthening measures to combat deforestation; stimulating a sustainable economy through regulations and tax incentives for the bioeconomy and socio-bioeconomic products; progressively aligning rural credit with the zero deforestation target; expanding financing for the recovery of pastures and degraded areas, and implementing the PES law, among others.
Sustenta.Bio Program - Alliance for strengthening socio-biodiversity economies in protected areas	Promotes the socio-bioeconomy in Extractive Reserves and other categories of protected areas that allow sustainable use by residents in the territories, combining income generation for local communities with biodiversity conservation and carbon emissions reduction.
Productive Forests Program	Seeks to restore forest areas that have been altered or degraded, expanding the capacity to produce healthy foods and socio-biodiversity products.
Forest+ Program	Aims to create, promote, and consolidate the market for environmental services, encouraging monetary and non-monetary compensation. The program focuses exclusively on areas of native vegetation and covers all categories of public or private land across all biomes.
Pronaf Florestas	Provides financing and technical assistance to family farmers to implement agroforestry systems and promote the conservation and sustainable management of natural resources on their rural properties.
Bioeconomy and Value Chains Project	Integrates climate protection and biodiversity in states in Brazil's Legal Amazon, promoting sustainable development, social inclusion, and forest preservation.

Instrumento	Sinergias Clima-Natureza
Resilient Marajó Project	Project in the Marajó archipelago that promotes agroforestry systems as climate adaptation solutions, integrating resilient agricultural practices with the preservation of local ecosystems.
Financing Program for Sustainable Agricultural Production Systems (RenovAgro)	Focused on financing low-carbon agriculture and activities compatible with standing forests, it prioritizes initiatives such as the recovery of degraded pastures (RenovAgro Recovery/Conversion), the implementation and improvement of crop-livestock-forest integration systems and agroforestry systems (RenovAgro Integration), and the adaptation or regularization of rural properties in line with environmental legislation, including the recovery of legal reserves, permanent preservation areas, degraded areas, and the implementation and improvement of sustainable forest management plans (RenovAgro Environmental).
Restore the Amazon	Supports ecological and/or productive restoration projects in the Amazon through non-reimbursable financing for ecological restoration with native species and/or agroforestry systems (SAFs).
Ecological Transformation Plan	National economic plan designed to combine employment and productivity, social justice, and environmental sustainability. Its goals encompass generating wealth while reducing the environmental impact of economic activity, easing pressure on ecosystems, and promoting low-carbon economies. It includes measures to cut greenhouse gas emissions, lower the environmental footprint of national economic development, encourage the sustainable use of natural resources and safeguard ecosystems.
EcoInvest Brazil Program - Mobilization of Foreign Private Capital and Exchange Rate Protection	Facilitates the attraction of foreign private investment for the ecological transition through mechanisms such as project structuring credit, liquidity and exchange rate volatility mitigation, currency hedging, and catalytic capital (blended finance). Sectors eligible for financing include ecosystem regeneration and actions in the bioeconomy and agri-food systems, based on the sustainable use of biological resources. Previous auctions have supported investments in the recovery of degraded pastures for food production.
Sustainable Sovereign Bonds	Public debt instruments for sustainable development designed to finance eligible activities, including greenhouse gas emissions control, the sustainable management of natural and biological resources and land use, terrestrial and aquatic biodiversity, and climate change adaptation.
Brazil Platform for Climate Investment and Ecological Transformation (BIP)	Created to scale up investments in decarbonization efforts, the Platform supports synergistic ecological transformation projects, particularly under its pillar focused on Nature-based Solutions and Bioeconomy.
National Fund on Climate Change	Supports climate projects related to native forests and water resources through conservation, restoration, and sustainable forest management, combining climate mitigation and resilience with environmental sustainability, water availability, and the protection and sustainable use of biodiversity.
Amazon Fund	Integrates solutions for tackling deforestation with forest ecosystem protection and emissions reduction, with a specific focus on the Brazilian Amazon.

Source: Igarapé Institute.

Synergies in the Brazilian Amazon

In the 2000s, especially until 2012, Brazil made significant progress in reducing deforestation, particularly in the Amazon. This achievement was driven by initiatives such as the Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Deforestation in the Legal Amazon (PPCDAm), launched in 2003. Command and control measures, the conditioning of rural credit on environmental compliance, and the prioritizing of municipalities with high deforestation rates also delivered significant results. At the same time, conservation units were expanded and Indigenous Lands were recognized, supported by programs such as the Amazon Protected Areas (Arpa) initiative and the Integrated Protection Project for Indigenous Peoples and Territories.⁵⁶

These initiatives not only reduced deforestation in the Amazon by a third at the time, but also made a major contribution to climate change mitigation by reducing GHG emissions from forest degradation. They also strengthened the rights of Indigenous peoples and traditional communities, while promoting biodiversity conservation and the maintenance of ecosystem services through the creation of the National System of Conservation Units. During that period, Brazil was responsible for the most significant global impact in terms of biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation.⁵⁷

However, in the following years, deforestation once again spiraled out of control, a situation aggravated by the economic and political crisis that began in the second half of the 2010s and became particularly acute between 2019 and 2022, when Brazil experienced severe setbacks in its environmental agenda, including the dismantling of public policies and institutions dedicated to environmental protection.⁵⁸

More recent data, however, points to signs of recovery. In 2023, gross greenhouse gas emissions fell to 2.3 billion tons of CO₂ equivalent (CO₂-eq), a 12% drop from the previous year and the lowest level in 15 years.

This decline was largely driven by a significant 37% reduction in deforestation in the Amazon.⁵⁹ Meanwhile, despite progress in reducing deforestation, forest degradation in the Amazon, caused by forest fires and illegal logging, increased by 497%, an alarming surge that reveals the complexity of the challenges ahead. This growth is directly linked to the rise in arson in areas of native vegetation, with impacts further intensified by extreme weather conditions. In 2024, the Amazon faced a second consecutive year of severe drought, worsening water stress and making the forest more vulnerable to fire, with fires even spreading to wetlands that had once served as natural barriers.⁶⁰

This situation underscores a major challenge for the region: while deforestation is being curbed, factors such as climate change and illegal activities continue to undermine the forest's resilience and capacity for regeneration. Forest degradation has far-reaching consequences, including biodiversity loss, carbon release, and a greater incidence in extreme weather events.

Since 2023, renewed momentum in environmental and climate agendas, together with update diagnoses and responses to a context different from the previous decade, has resulted in a new set of actions, especially at the federal-level actions, starting with the new PPCDAm. At the same time, public policy instruments have expanded, including credit and financing for Amazonian territories, such as the Amazon Fund and Pronaf Floresta, in addition to other actions such as PGPMBio and the Productive Forests Program (see Table 1). Many of these initiatives are still at an early stage and will need to mature and be reinforced in order to generate synergistic outcomes across the climate, nature, and inclusive and sustainable development agendas.

3. CLIMATE-NATURE SYNERGIES AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL: AMAZON BASIN

This section discusses the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda at the regional level in the Amazon Basin. It identifies initiatives in the Pan-Amazon region led by regional organizations such as the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) and the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB), alongside examples of national initiatives across the region — from policies and projects to the diplomatic leadership of other South American countries such as Colombia. The section emphasizes that tackling deforestation, conserving socio-biodiversity, and promoting sustainable development in the Pan-Amazon region require actions that transcend national borders, making it essential to further strengthen technical and political dialogue and enhance regional cooperation in the Amazon Basin around the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda.

3.1 Climate-Nature Synergies and Amazonian cooperation

Tropical forests such as the Amazon Basin provide fertile ground for innovation and experimentation within the climate–nature synergies agenda, enabling commitments made under the Rio Conventions to be translated and implemented in critical territories. It is, therefore, an implementation-driven agenda.

The ecological importance of the biome, along with the need to establish mechanisms for its management and conservation beyond the borders of the national states that make up the Basin, gave rise to the Amazonian consultation, coordination, and cooperation efforts⁶¹ culminating in the signing

of the Amazon Cooperation Treaty (ACT) in 1978 and the creation of the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) in 1995. Since its inception, ACTO has been committed to promoting sustainable development in the Amazon region, integrating biodiversity conservation with economic and social prosperity. Its mandate reflects the understanding that these pillars are interdependent and essential for the region’s balance. The Organization grounds its actions on principles that promote cooperation among member countries, recognizing the Amazon as a vital ecosystem not only for biodiversity and sustainable development in South America, but also for global climate security.

The treaty establishing ACTO reaffirms the commitment of its members to “act in accordance with the principle of sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, in harmony with nature and the environment”.⁶² This commitment is even more relevant today, given the critical importance of preserving the Amazon — the world’s largest tropical forest — in the face of the triple planetary crisis, and its contribution to global climate stability and biodiversity conservation. In addition, ACTO’s mandate prioritizes the coordination of environmental, climate, development, and more recently public security policies,⁶³ which are essential to address cross-border challenges that threaten the region’s integrity, including the urgent need to end deforestation and tackle organized environmental crime.⁶⁴

The Belém and Bogotá Declarations, adopted at the Amazon Summits of 2023 and 2025,⁶⁵ underscores the climate-nature synergy agenda, highlighting the Amazon’s importance for global climate security and its crucial role in strengthening resilience to the

impacts of climate change. The Declarations also emphasize the need for a sustainable development paradigm that integrates social, economic, and environmental dimensions, promoting the responsible use of natural resources, rule of law, the strengthening of local livelihoods, and the valuation of ecosystem services provided by the forest.⁶⁶

With its mandate and network, ACTO is well positioned to lead the regional development of an integrated model for development and conservation in the Amazon. By aligning climate and biodiversity agendas, promoting innovative financial mechanisms, and institutionalizing cross-border cooperation, ACTO has the potential to turn the region into a global example of integrated regional environmental governance. However, the success of this model depends on strengthening ACTO itself and its capacity to foster intergovernmental cooperation on the climate-nature synergy agenda. This includes supporting countries in harmonizing regulatory frameworks, coordinating and sharing public policies and technologies, and implementing concrete actions to preserve biodiversity, mitigate climate change impacts, and promote local development compatible with the standing forest.

Although modest in scale, ACTO has developed technical cooperation initiatives that demonstrate climate-nature synergies at the regional level in the Pan-Amazon. Among the ongoing initiatives is the *Bioamazônia Project*,⁶⁷ aimed at strengthening the management, monitoring, and control of wild fauna and flora species threatened by trade, especially those included in the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (Cites). Past initiatives include projects like the *Forest Cover Monitoring in the Amazon Region and the Monitoring of Deforestation, Forest Use and Land Use Change in the Pan-Amazon Forest*,⁶⁸ implemented between 2011 and 2018, which sought to strengthen forest cover monitoring systems in member countries. Another

example is the ACTO Biomaz Project: Support to the *ACTO biodiversity program under the CBD Framework in Latin America*. The project sought to develop a consensus framework or program among member countries for the sustainable use and conservation of the Amazon biodiversity, generate data on the status and trends of biodiversity and ecosystem services, and foster dialogue and the exchange of experiences among experts and civil servants across the Basin.⁶⁹

In addition to ACTO's regional initiatives, the Science Panel for the Amazon (SPA)⁷⁰ has emerged as a key scientific platform for promoting synergies between the agendas for combating climate change and protecting biodiversity in the region. In its Amazon Assessment Report 2021⁷¹, the Panel reinforced the importance of integrating biodiversity conservation with climate action, highlighting the Amazon's critical role as a global climate regulator and one of the planet's largest reservoirs of biodiversity. In addition, during the COP16 Biodiversity Conference in 2024, the SPA presented a Policy Brief⁷² proposing the creation of a network of innovation hubs to promote regenerative bioeconomies in the region, integrating science, technology, and traditional knowledge. These scientific contributions provide practical guidance for strengthening regional cooperation and advancing a development model that reconciles environmental protection and climate resilience.

This set of initiatives illustrates the growing interest in the synergies agenda and the emergence of more integrated approaches at the regional level. Given the current volume and scale of actions explicitly designed to foster complementarity between these agendas, it is clear that there is still room to deepen and institutionalize efforts at the regional level, as well as expand the thematic scope of cooperation. Within ACTO, this could mean complementing the more traditional focus on natural heritage preservation with projects that advance sustainable and inclusive development solutions in areas such as the bioeconomy.⁷³

3.2 Climate-Nature Synergies in financing sustainable development and policies in the Pan-Amazon

In parallel with the efforts of regional institutions, recent years have seen the emergence of several national and multilateral initiatives that also support the implementation of climate-nature synergies at the domestic level and across countries in the region. Among these are projects led by Latin American multilateral financial institutions, such as the Inter-American Development Bank (IDB) and, to a lesser extent, the Development Bank of Latin America (CAF).

Within the IDB, the Amazon Forever Program⁷⁴, launched in 2023, stands out. It adopts an integrated approach aimed at preserving the Amazon as a global biodiversity and climate asset. This innovative umbrella program provides a framework for regional coordination of sustainable and inclusive development in the Amazon. It finances and supports local actors in actions that promote nature-based solutions, strengthen Indigenous communities, and foster sustainable infrastructure, while prioritizing the protection of the region's natural resources.

The program currently covers more than 270 projects and a portfolio of operations exceeding USD 5 billion. Through its portfolio, Amazon Forever mobilizes financing for climate and conservation actions, encouraging public-private partnerships and community engagement as key elements for achieving lasting results. Its priority areas include combating deforestation, promoting the bioeconomy and creative economy, advancing inclusive social development, strengthening sustainable cities, and supporting low-carbon agriculture adapted to the Amazon context⁷⁵ Among the many initiatives relevant to the climate-nature synergies agenda, the Amazonia Bonds— launched in

2024 and aligned with the principles for green, social, and sustainability bonds⁷⁶, — stand out as a mechanism to leverage responsible capital for climate and nature finance in the region. The Bank also supports regional networks such as the Pan-Amazonian Network for the Bioeconomy and the Bioamazon Network of Research and Innovation Institutes in Biodiversity, both focused on promoting the Amazon bioeconomy while creating opportunities for local populations and ensuring the conservation of the standing forest.

For its part, CAF has sought to integrate climate and biodiversity agendas through strategic investments aimed at protecting key ecosystems in the Amazon. With a planned contribution of USD 2 billion by 2030,⁷⁷ CAF focuses on developing sustainable production chains, building resilient cities, and restoring degraded areas. In partnership with ICLEI, the global association of local and subnational governments, the bank has also worked to incorporate biodiversity into urban policies, reaffirming its commitment to sustainable development and environmental protection.⁷⁸

Finally, alongside the regional actions led by ACTO, the work of the SPA, and the activities of regional multilateral banks such as the IDB and CAF, other Amazonian countries – much like Brazil (see Section 2) – have also made progress nationally and through partnership with neighboring countries in developing policies and projects that connect biodiversity and climate change agendas. Table 2 below presents some of these initiatives (including projects, public policies, financing mechanisms, and cooperation projects), offering concrete examples of how countries in the region are already promoting climate-nature synergies on the ground.

Table 2. Instruments and initiatives that promote climate-nature synergies in the Pan-Amazon

Category	Country	Instruments and initiatives	Description
National Strategic Policies and Actions	Colombia Peru and Suriname	National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plans (NBSAPs) ⁷⁹	National plans for biodiversity conservation aligned with CBD targets, including climate actions and recognizing the synergies between the climate and biodiversity agendas.
	Colombia	Strategy 2050 (E2050) ⁸⁰	Long-term strategies for carbon neutrality and climate resilience that connect biodiversity conservation with the green economy.
	Colombia	Diplomacy for Climate-Nature Synergies	The Colombian government has been actively engaged in diplomacy on the Rio Conventions Synergies Agenda, particularly regarding climate and biodiversity, and has placed this issue at the center of its COP16 Biodiversity Presidency in 2024 (see Section 4).
	Venezuela	Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) ⁸¹	Venezuela has updated its climate change commitments to include adaptation and mitigation measures that account for biodiversity conservation, reflecting an integrated approach to the country's environmental challenges.
Financial Instruments and Financing Mechanisms	Bolivia	Plurinational Climate Change Policy ⁸²	Policy framework that guides public policies to integrate climate adaptation and biodiversity preservation.
	Ecuador, Colombia, Panama, and Costa Rica	Multi-donor fund for the Chocó Biogeographic Region and other related eco-regions ⁸³	Financial mechanism that channels international resources for biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation in the Chocó Biogeographic Region, and related eco-regions, in partnership with the Development Bank of Latin America (CAF).
	Peru	Works for Taxes e Invierte.pe ⁸⁴	Tax incentive scheme that allows private companies to allocate up to 50% of their eligible taxes to public infrastructure projects, including nature-positive initiatives such as biodiversity protection and Nature-based Solutions.

Category	Country	Instruments and initiatives	Description
Bioeconomy and Payment for Environmental Services (PES) Programs and Projects	French Guiana	Action Plan on Bioeconomy and Tropical Forest Protection ⁸⁵	Action plan to establish a bioeconomy model that integrates the social, economic, and environmental dimensions of sustainable development, contributing to climate change mitigation and poverty.
	Bolivia	Sovereign Carbon Market ⁸⁶	Framework that establishes a national carbon market to generate resources and finance sovereign efforts to combat deforestation, while supporting biodiversity conservation projects.
	Colombia	Biocultural Pacific Program ⁸⁷	Program that integrates biodiversity conservation with sustainable development in coastal and forest areas.
Regional Governance and Cooperation	Brazil and French Guiana	Brazil-French Guiana Cross-Border Environmental Cooperation ⁸⁸	Bilateral agreement focused on combating environmental crimes in border regions, preserving natural areas, conserving biodiversity, restoring degraded areas, and addressing biopiracy and wildlife trafficking.
	Argentina, Bolivia, Colombia, Chile, Ecuador, Peru, and Venezuela	Andean Mountain Initiative ⁸⁹	Regional platform composed of the seven countries that share the Andes Mountains. On a voluntary basis, these countries work to strengthen regional dialogue, promote and implement joint actions for the conservation and sustainable development of the Andean region.
	Inter-American Development Bank	Amazon Forever Program ⁹⁰	Program designed to expand financing, share strategic knowledge, and enhance regional coordination to accelerate sustainable, inclusive, and resilient development in the Amazon. By integrating climate action and forest conservation, the program prioritizes sustainable agriculture, forestry, and the bioeconomy, among other key areas.

Source: Igarapé Institute

4. SYNERGIES AT THE GLOBAL LEVEL: MULTILATERAL SPACES

This final section addresses the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda at the global level, with a focus on multilateral initiatives within the United Nations (UN) system and other international forums. This section highlights diplomatic efforts within multilateral bodies, as well as contributions from the scientific community and civil society, to promote greater dialogue among the Rio Conventions. It underscores the growing importance of this agenda and the progress achieved in recent years, especially the bridges beginning to be built within the Convention on Biological Diversity. Finally, it points to the most promising opportunities for this agenda to gain more weight within the Climate Convention, starting with COP30 in Brazil and the Amazon.

4.1 Synergies in the Rio Conventions: the multilateral debate

Global environmental governance is shaped by a series of distinct agreements. Instruments such as the UNFCCC, the CBD, and the UNCCD — also known as the Rio Conventions, as they originated from the Rio Eco-92 (see Section 1) — form part of a complex web of multilateral mechanisms designed to address the climate and ecological crises. In this framework, environmental commitments intersect with non-environmental commitments and initiatives, such as the SDGs, as well as the activities of multilateral development banks and environmental and climate funds.

However, in practice, this set of instruments tends to operate in parallel, leading to overlaps, gaps, and at times even conflicts between their

objectives.⁹¹ This is far from a new diagnosis — or one limited to environmental agreements. Fragmentation, duplication, and competition between international instruments continue to pose major challenges to advancing synergistic actions that address climate change and nature protection. These challenges are further compounded by the broader crisis in UN multilateralism and global governance, marked by the rise of nationalism and authoritarianism in different parts of the world, with repercussions for climate governance.⁹²

Despite undeniable achievements,⁹³ the Climate Conferences of the Parties (Climate COPs) have also faced growing criticism, particularly due to the exhaustion of the current model. One concern is the consensus-based decision-making process, which allows individual countries to slow or block progress, especially in the transition away from fossil fuels, often resulting in weakened agreements despite the urgency of the climate crisis. Another recurring concern relates to the COPs' limited capacity to ensure and support the effective implementation of commitments negotiated over the last few decades, especially since the Paris Agreement.⁹⁴

In other words, there are persistent questions about the effectiveness of multilateral processes such as the Climate COPs in turning agreed commitments into concrete public policies, including those reiterated in the latest Global Stocktake (GST) concluded at COP28 in 2023.⁹⁵

The issue of synergies is itself a further source of concern. A central challenge lies in the absence of clear and effective multilateral mechanisms to align the climate and biodiversity agendas. While the UNFCCC relies on quantitative targets, such as achieving

emissions neutrality by 2050 (Article 4.1 of the Paris Agreement), biodiversity cannot be captured by a single indicator, making it inherently more complex to set targets and evaluate policies.

In addition, within the financing pillar of both agendas, significant gaps between internationally agreed commitments — especially those made by developed countries to support developing countries — and the actual mobilization of resources. At the same time, synergistic international financing, such as in the case of NbS, still represents only a small share of total flows. According to 2021 data, approximately USD 133 billion per year is currently allocated to NbS, mostly from public sources, which is low compared to spending on the energy transition or to subsidies for activities that degrade nature.⁹⁶

Challenges also persist with voluntary and market-based approaches⁹⁷ which, despite their growing popularity, have shown limited and not yet fully understood impacts, especially in the context of NbS and nature finance. Evidence indicates that their contribution to emissions reductions remains constrained and, to be effective, they must be complemented by more robust and ambitious public policies. Such policies should aim to increase public financing, mobilize private capital as catalytic capital, and to provide guarantees and other de-risking instruments, including exchange rate guarantees, while also ensuring the integrity of market-based solutions.⁹⁸

The REDD+ carbon credit mechanism, created under the UNFCCC to reduce emissions from deforestation and forest degradation, has demonstrated that its effectiveness depends on a participatory design that ensures fair compensation mechanisms and equitable distribution of benefits and costs. Without such a structure, there is a risk of exacerbating inequalities and generating negative impacts on vulnerable communities.⁹⁹ In both REDD+ and the still-emerging carbon markets and

biodiversity credits or certificates, integrity challenges persist.¹⁰⁰ Moreover, carbon markets under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement remain in the early stages of development and will require consolidation efforts at the national level, along with guarantees of interoperability, not only between regulated and voluntary markets within countries,¹⁰¹ but also across jurisdictions.

Finally, the lack of coherence and integration across sectors and policy scales continues to be a major obstacle. The Rio Conventions — UNFCCC, CBD, and UNCCD — each carry negotiation agendas that reflect the diverse interests of their parties, which often translate into fragmented approaches when shaping national policies and instruments. While opportunities for more integrated governance do exist, significant barriers remain to cooperation among multiple actors and across different levels of governance.¹⁰²

In the current scenario, international cooperation plays an even more critical role in advancing the implementation of the Paris Agreement and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KM-GBF). It is essential to recognize the progress already achieved through international cooperation in addressing global challenges, while also acknowledging the need for reforms in existing structures and arrangements. Such reforms are necessary to promote greater coherence and synergy between the climate and nature agendas, ensuring the effective and integrated implementation of multilateral agreements.

Although still emerging, there are numerous proposals for innovative approaches to foster climate-nature synergies on a global scale, combining adaptive tools and cross-sectoral solutions, as discussed below.

4.2 Scientific basis and ancestral knowledge

Scientific evidence has been crucial for building climate-nature synergies. In 2003, the CBD published Technical Study No. 10,¹⁰³ one of the first technical and scientific efforts aimed at integrating the biodiversity and climate agendas. The study recommended incorporating biodiversity considerations into the implementation of the Climate Convention and its Kyoto Protocol. It was prepared by an ad hoc technical group with support from SBSTTA (the CBD's scientific subsidiary body), drawing on evidence from the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) and experts across multiple fields.

In 2019, the Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services (IPBES) identified climate change as the third leading driver of biodiversity loss, after land use change and the direct exploitation of species. The report identified the urgent need to protect between 30% and 50% of the planet's land, freshwater, and oceans to prevent irreversible impacts.¹⁰⁴

The concept of [ecosystem integrity](#) (see Glossary), which appears in both the Paris Agreement and the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report, is central to aligning ecosystem-based strategies with climate mitigation goals. It provides a scientific framework for minimizing the risks of ecosystem-based policies while maximizing carbon stocks and collateral benefits.¹⁰⁵ In a landmark collaboration, the joint workshop of the IPCC and IPBES in 2021 marked the first formal interaction between the two intergovernmental scientific panels. The resulting report¹⁰⁶ mapped complex connections between the two agendas, proposing coordinated actions that enhance [co-benefits and minimize trade-offs](#) (see Glossary).

Building on the long-standing efforts by Indigenous peoples and traditional communities, especially in forest areas, whose

ancestral knowledge — or Indigenous science — has long addressed climate and biodiversity in an integrated manner, there is now a growing consensus on the importance of climate-nature synergies. Within climate science, the next frontier is to advance synergistic approaches to knowledge production and evidence generation that can inform international climate action. This includes, for example, developing carbon neutrality models that guide public policies for climate and nature.¹⁰⁷

4.3 Conferences of the Parties (COPs)

A more integrated approach, with stronger intersectoral policy action and coordinated governance between institutions and the strategic goals of the 1992 Rio Conventions on climate and biodiversity (UNFCCC and CBD) — is essential to align biodiversity conservation objectives with climate mitigation and adaptation actions. Despite the difficulties, a number of initiatives and proposals have sought to promote greater integration between these agendas. Since the creation of the Joint Liaison Group (JLG) in 2001, efforts have been made to foster cooperation among the Rio Conventions.¹⁰⁸ These efforts have begun to show results, with references to synergies becoming increasingly frequent in documents and decisions from different multilateral processes (see Table 3 below).¹⁰⁹ This includes, for example, decisions under the Convention on Desertification, such as Decision 8 of COP16 in 2024, which strongly emphasizes the need to connect the agendas of the three Rio Conventions.

In recent years, the interconnection between climate and nature has been increasingly recognized at key global milestones. Two fundamental instruments in this context are the Paris Agreement itself and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, which establish commitments to address the climate crisis and the biodiversity loss crisis,

respectively. In addition, recent decisions adopted at UNFCCC and CBD conferences, along with statements from global leaders, have further reinforced this alignment, helping to advance the integration of these agendas (see Table 3).

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KM-GBF): Adopted at CBD COP15 in 2022, the KM-GBF sets ambitious targets to halt and reverse biodiversity loss by 2030 through ecosystem restoration, the protection of natural areas, and by strengthening ecosystem resilience to climate change. While all GBF targets are in some way related to climate change, especially in terms of adaptation, several are explicitly linked to this theme. These include Target 2 (ecosystem restoration); Target 8 (biodiversity resilience to climate change); Target 11 (nature-based solutions for the benefit of people and the planet); and Target 19 (e) (optimizing the co-benefits and synergies of financial flows simultaneously targeting the climate and biodiversity crises).¹¹⁰ Since its adoption, some Member States, including Amazonian countries such as Colombia and Brazil (see Sections 2 and 3), have championed efforts to strengthen dialogue between the Conventions. Political and diplomatic momentum in this direction was visible during COP16 in Cali in 2024, the first held since the adoption of the Global Framework.

Paris Agreement: Adopted in 2015 under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, the Paris Agreement also incorporates elements linking climate protection with biodiversity conservation. Article 4.1(d) invites all Parties to promote sustainable management and cooperate in the conservation and enhancement of greenhouse gas sinks and reservoirs, including biomass, forests, oceans, and other terrestrial, coastal, and marine ecosystems. Article 5 expands on this commitment, introducing specific guidelines with an emphasis on forests. It promotes incentive mechanisms such as REDD+, which operates through carbon credits and aims to reduce emissions from deforestation and forest degradation, while also supporting conservation, sustainable forest management, and the enhancement of forest carbon stocks.

Table 3. Synergistic COP Decisions and Declarations Bridging the Climate and Biodiversity Agendas

Convention	Decisions	Declarations
<p style="text-align: center;">CBD</p>	<p>COP16 (Cali, 2024): Decision 16/22¹¹¹ mandates the CBD Executive Secretary to collect, by May 2025, proposals to enhance policy coherence among the Rio Conventions and to consider the possible establishment of a Joint Work Program (JWP). In addition, the Executive Secretaries of all three Rio Conventions were invited to collaborate in 2024 to explore ways to promote greater cooperation and alignment between the objectives of the Global Biodiversity Framework and the Paris Agreement.</p>	<p>COP16 (Cali, 2024): Open letter to Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva and Gustavo Petro¹¹² More than 70 global leaders signed an open letter addressed to Presidents Gustavo Petro and Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva, acknowledging their leadership in integrating the climate, biodiversity, and food systems agendas. The letter called for a global mobilization of unified actions between Cali, host of COP16, and Belém, host of COP30.</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">UNFCCC</p>	<p>COP27 (Sharm el-Sheikh, 2022): 1/CP.27 (Sharm el-Sheikh Implementation Plan):¹¹³ Reinforced the need to address the climate change and biodiversity loss crises in an integrated manner, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).</p> <p>COP28 (Dubai, 2023): 1/CMA.5 (Global Stocktake)¹¹⁴, paragraph 33. Emphasized the conservation and restoration of terrestrial and marine ecosystems to achieve the goals of the Paris Agreement, including efforts to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation by 2030. Meanwhile, 2/CMA.5 (Global Goal on Adaptation).¹¹⁵ included reducing climate impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity through the promotion of nature-based solutions.</p>	<p>COP26 (Glasgow, 2021): Glasgow Leaders’ Declaration on Forests and Land Use.¹¹⁶ A total of 145 world leaders committed to work collectively to halt and reverse forest loss and land degradation by 2030.</p> <p>COP28 (Dubai, 2023): Joint Statement on Climate, Nature and People by the presidencies of the UNFCCC and CBD, and supported by 18 countries.¹¹⁷</p> <p>COP29 (Baku, 2024): COP29 Nature Statement:¹¹⁸ Published by a coalition of more than 100 NGOs, business coalitions, companies, Indigenous peoples’ organizations, and influential individuals. It called for a new, fair, and ambitious Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG) aligned with the synergies between Rio Conventions, while highlighting the importance of climate finance that respects the rights of Indigenous peoples and local communities.</p>

Source: Igarapé Institute.

4.4 Global initiatives and proposals

The decisions and declarations of recent COPs, combined with growing recognition of the role of forests in the climate agenda and the importance of ecosystem restoration and integrity, have driven a wide range of initiatives promoted by civil society organizations, academia, multilateral bodies, global leaders, and coalitions. Figure 1 below features examples of global initiatives that emphasize synergies, with particular attention to forests, which by their very nature already represent a natural point of convergence between the climate and nature agendas.

Some of these initiatives stem from the activism of COP presidencies, State Parties, or the work of UN agencies and their secretariats. Others emerge from proposals and ongoing efforts by civil society organizations and experts to develop concrete proposals that promote greater synergy between the climate and nature agendas. As illustrated in Figure 1 below, there has been a concentration of initiatives and proposals in the last decade, especially since the 2020s, reflecting the growing relevance of the debate.

Figure 1. Timeline: Progress on the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda at the Global Level

(2022) Forest & Climate Leaders' Partnership (FCLP): Works to reduce forest loss, foster restoration, and ensure compliance with climate commitments. By bringing together committed governments and organizations, the partnership also promotes accountability for conservation pledges made in international forums.

(2023) Climate Nature Coordination Platform (CNCP):¹¹⁹ Created from the COP28 Joint Statement on Climate, Nature, and People to coordinate synergistic actions between climate and biodiversity agendas. Now called Synergies Collaboration Platform, it seeks to promote integrated initiatives that simultaneously address climate and ecological challenges.

(2023) Grupo Unidos por Nossas Florestas: Launched during the ACTO Amazon Summit in Belém, it brings together countries such as Brazil, Colombia, Indonesia, and the Democratic Republic of Congo to strengthen cooperation for the preservation of tropical forests. Beyond coordination in multilateral spaces, such as the Climate and Biodiversity COPs, the group seeks to advance financial mechanisms adapted to regional specificities, including the Tropical Forests Forever Facility (TFFF).

(2023) Tropical Forests Forever Facility (TFFF): An initiative led by Brazil to expand access to resources for tropical forest conservation through an innovative mechanism that uses investment returns to value the global environmental services provided by tropical forests. It seeks to reward tropical forest countries for their conservation efforts. The Brazilian government plans to launch the mechanism during COP30.

(2024) Proposal for a multidisciplinary Ad Hoc Technical Group (AHTEG):¹²⁰ Proposed by the Climate Action Network (CAN) to support the implementation of Article 5 of the Paris Agreement. The group would strengthen carbon sinks and preserve ecological integrity by developing ecosystem monitoring indicators, identifying financing and technical capacity gaps, and promoting alignment with international frameworks such as the KM-GBF. It would include technical experts, Indigenous peoples, local communities, and youth, ensuring an inclusive and science-based approach.

(2024) Joint Work Program for Climate and Nature:¹²¹ Proposed by WWF, this initiative establishes a four-year roadmap to implement key decisions from COP26, COP27, and the United Arab Emirates Consensus from COP28. It seeks to align national climate and biodiversity plans (NDCs, National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans - NBSAPs, and National Adaptation Plans - NAPs), optimize financing mechanisms for projects with co-benefits, and address implementation challenges. The roadmap foresees thematic workshops and reports to be presented at ministerial meetings at future COPs.

(2024) Guidelines for integrating biodiversity into climate action at COP29:¹²² Developed by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), the guidelines recommend incorporating biodiversity and ecosystem integrity into Paris Agreement implementation. Key recommendations include applying ecological safeguards in Article 6 projects, adopting the IUCN Global Standard for Nature-based Solutions, and including nature-related targets in the new NDCs. The guidelines also reinforce the importance of synergies between the three Rio Conventions.

(2025) Proposals to enhance policy coherence among the Rio Conventions.

In response to Decision 16/22 (see Table 3), the CBD Secretariat received contributions on a possible creation of a Joint Work Program (JWP). Submissions included proposals from Brazil, Colombia, Peru, and six other countries and the European Union (with all its members) totaling 10 contributions from Parties and 59 from observer organizations, including United Nations agencies and civil society organizations.¹²³

(2025) Fifth Global Dialogue of the Sharm el-Sheikh Work Program on Mitigation Ambition and Implementation (MWP): Held in Panama City, the fifth global dialogue focused on forest-sector mitigation solutions, based on national and regional experiences.

(2025) First technical exchange: Organized by the CBD Secretariat in partnership with the other Rio Convention Secretariats, this exchange — in Bonn and on the margins of the UNFCCC Subsidiary Body Sessions (SB62) — explored options for enhancing cooperation and coherence among the Conventions.¹²⁴

5. ADVANCING THE CLIMATE-NATURE SYNERGIES AGENDA AT COP30

In a context of growing international mobilization around the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda, as reflected in the timeline above, COP30 is a key moment to advance this debate. The conference takes place at a decisive juncture to both Brazil and the world, amid a crisis of multilateralism and declining confidence in collective climate action. Since the adoption of the Paris Agreement in 2015, challenges such as the rise of authoritarianism and regional conflicts, inconsistent participation by the United States, and the surpassing of the 1.5°C warming threshold in 2024 have underscored the need for even more vigorous mobilization to leverage collective responses.

As one of the most active voices in the Global South and home to 60% of the Amazon, Brazil has the potential to lead a just and green global transition, addressing internal challenges while serving as an example for balancing conservation, social inclusion, and sustainable growth. COP30 will also be the first Climate COP held in the Amazon rainforest, offering a historic opportunity to highlight forests as carbon sinks through restoration, rather than as emitters as a result of deforestation.

The central role of forests in Belém and their relevance in addressing the climate crisis were highlighted by Ambassador André Corrêa do Lago in the first letter from the COP30 Presidency, which outlined Brazil's vision for the conference. In the second letter — marking the transition from vision to action — Corrêa do Lago broadened the scope, framing nature in a more systemic way. The letter calls for urgent and integrated responses, with an emphasis on forest restoration, the recovery of degraded lands, and the strengthening

of coastal ecosystems as strategic tools for both emissions mitigation and adaptation. Although the term “synergies” is not explicitly used, the message reinforces that nature-based solutions are essential to accelerate greenhouse gases removal and strengthen climate resilience, especially in a context that demands immediate action.¹²⁵

The term, however, appears in the 8th Letter from the Presidency, in which Corrêa do Lago states that Nature-based Solutions and synergies between climate and biodiversity can accelerate this transition toward “adaptation economies” that protect nature while fostering resilient and climate-smart economies.¹²⁶

This perspective is reflected in Brazil's commitment to strengthening climate governance and integrating different international mechanisms, as proposed through the Circle of Presidencies, which will convene leaders from previous COPs as well as from the Conventions on Biological Diversity and Desertification.

Launched on June 20,¹²⁷ the Action Agenda is organized into six priority areas to support the implementation of the Global Stocktake (GST). Regarding the climate-nature nexus, priority area (ii) stands out: “Stewarding Forests, Oceans, and Biodiversity” is particularly relevant. It calls for integrated actions to accelerate solutions regarding: (5) investments to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation, (6) efforts to conserve, protect and restore nature and ecosystems with solutions addressing climate, biodiversity and desertification, and (7) measures to preserve and restore oceans and coastal ecosystems.

At the same time, Brazil is expected to advance initiatives such as the United for Our Forests Group and to launch the TFFF at COP30, underscoring its leadership and commitment to forest conservation. Brazil also has the opportunity to contribute to the synergies agenda through one of its main deliverables under the Baku to Belém Roadmap to 1.3 T. This includes explicit references to the promotion of synergistic financing instruments, the development of criteria for financing, and the provision of financial incentives for ecological restoration and the bioeconomy.

Within the Negotiating Agenda, progress on climate-biodiversity synergies – referred to here as biodiversity, in alignment with the CBD – will depend above all on the engagement of the Parties and the work of the UNFCCC

secretariat. Although the Brazilian presidency of COP30 can exert political influence and catalyze support among the Parties, it does not have a formal mandate to set the agenda or conduct negotiations. The inclusion of topics on the agenda and the adoption of decisions depend on consensus among countries, in accordance with the rules that guide UNFCCC's multilateral processes.

Nevertheless, the growing international recognition of the interdependence between the climate and nature agendas, together with the symbolism of a COP held in the Amazon, may help create favorable conditions for significant progress. Among the most concrete entry points for this agenda in the COP30 negotiations, and in subsequent ones, the following options stand out.¹²⁸

- **A decision under the SBSTA (UNFCCC Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice)** on cooperation with other international organizations, a particularly promising avenue given the positive outcome achieved in Bonn during SB62 (see below). This progress paves the way for discussions to resume at COP30 and could lead to the adoption of a formal decision on synergies between the Rio Conventions.
- **A decision within the context of the Global Stocktake**, based on the outcomes of the Dubai Dialogue (UAE Dialogue), which explicitly highlights the integration between the climate and biodiversity agendas.
- **A decision under the Sharm el-Sheikh Work Program on Ambition and Implementation of Mitigation (MWP)**, referring to the results of the dialogue on forest sector mitigation solutions held during Panama Climate Week.
- **A decision in the main text of COP30 (cover decision)**, proposing the establishment of an Ad Hoc Technical Expert Group (AHTEG) and requesting the Executive Secretariat to strengthen collaboration with the secretariats of the other Rio Conventions, including through the development of a Joint Work Programme.
- **The creation of a stand-alone agenda item on synergies between the Rio Conventions**, accompanied by a decision establishing an AHTEG and formally launching a Joint Work Programme.

SB62 – Progress on Synergies within the UNFCCC towards COP30

Following the first technical exchange between the secretariats of the Rio Conventions, significant progress was made to strengthen synergies between the three Conventions during the 62nd session of the UNFCCC Subsidiary Bodies, held in Bonn in June 2025. The agenda advanced within the formal negotiation process, with particular emphasis on the item on international cooperation (SBSTA 14), which officially launched discussions on synergies between the Conventions, in preparation for a potential decision at COP30. The approved text¹²⁹ — led by Colombia — invites Parties and observers to submit contributions by September 30, 2025, and highlights the importance of expanding and making existing collaborations and making them more inclusive. Colombia continues to lead these efforts, with Brazil playing a strategic role in its capacity as COP30 Presidency.

Throughout the two weeks of SB62, a series of side and external events addressed the theme of synergies from multiple perspectives, reflecting the growing international interest. Highlights included the high-level event organized by the COP30 Presidency, “Bringing the Legacy of Rio to Belém,” as well as receptions hosted by Germany and Colombia on cooperation among the Conventions. The UNFCCC Secretariat also contributed with side events focused on synergistic implementation and joint capacity building. In addition, several civil society organizations, think tanks, and universities organized events exploring nature-based solutions, a positive energy transition for nature, and the role of tropical forests in climate and biodiversity synergies.

CONCLUSION

The Climate-Nature Synergy Agenda is already taking shape. At the multilateral level, there is growing recognition of the interdependence between the climate and nature agendas, with concrete proposals and progress in recent years, both in the political and diplomatic spheres and in the work carried out by the bodies that make up the Rio Conventions. At the implementation level, several countries and regions, including Brazil and the Amazon Basin, have demonstrated remarkable dynamism.

In Brazil, the wide range of initiatives and actions mapped throughout this study indicate that the country has the diplomatic will and a solid foundation of structured solutions, effective instruments, and technical capacity to advance the twin agendas of combating climate change and conserving biodiversity. This progress is driven by an approach that links environmental conservation with sustainable and inclusive development. The Brazilian Amazon stands out as a key arena for much of this experimentation, though it is far from being the only hub of innovation.

Both in Brazil and beyond, the Amazon Basin — the world's largest tropical forest — is not only one of the epicenters of the climate crisis and biodiversity loss, but also a source of climate solutions and action, including through promoting climate-nature synergies for environmental conservation and sustainable development. Regionally, across the Pan-Amazon region, there is a growing number of actions to promote climate-nature synergies underway at the national, bilateral, and multilateral levels, within and between different Amazonian countries, and led by regional organizations and initiatives.

However, while progress has been significant, it is important to recognize not only the incipient nature of some of these initiatives, but also the need to consistently channel resources toward

improving and expanding existing policies, instruments, and projects. In countries like Brazil, strengthening the implementation of synergistic initiatives requires expanding and sustaining political commitment (including at the subnational level), ensuring strategic financial allocation, enhancing state capabilities, and engaging different sectors of government and society. These efforts are essential to mitigate integrity risks and to expand positive impacts on both national sustainable development and the global response to the climate and biodiversity loss crises.

In the Pan-Amazon region, efforts to combat deforestation, protect socio-biodiversity, and promote sustainable development demand actions that transcend national borders. As ACTO member countries seek to deepen regional cooperation, the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda offers a promising platform for sharing experiences and promoting innovative solutions tailored to the realities of the region. Supporting national and regional public policies and integrating climate, nature, and sustainable development agendas are also essential to ensure that countries in the region meet their climate and biodiversity commitments while advancing sustainable development that respects the rights and needs of Amazonian populations. In this context, bilateral or multilateral technical cooperation among countries, along with financial and technical support from initiatives such as the Amazon Forever Program and others, will be important partnerships for governments and regional bodies such as ACTO, helping to strengthen state capacities and advance the implementation of increasingly synergistic conservation and sustainable development policies and projects.

Finally, at the multilateral level, although the most recent advances have taken place within the framework of the Convention on

Biological Diversity, aimed at achieving greater policy coherence with the climate agenda, there is now growing openness to advancing this discussion within climate negotiations as well. In the year when the Climate COP will be held in the Amazon — a critical ecosystem for both agendas — there is a unique window of opportunity to reach new consensus and solidify the importance of the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda.

Strengthening this agenda within the UN system is crucial to consolidate and accelerate the progress being made in countries such as Brazil, and others across the Amazon Basin, as well as in global institutions like the Multilateral Development Banks. There is no doubt that the multilateral context remains delicate and that there are multiple concrete paths for incorporating this issue into the negotiations, the Action Agenda and related processes. However, it falls to Brazil, as President of COP30, to lead efforts and build consensus to secure these advances, whether through the Action Agenda, the high-level segment or in COP30 negotiations in Belém in 2025. By doing so, Brazil will make a tangible contribution to advancing the implementation of the Rio Conventions — a stated priority of its COP30 Presidency — while simultaneously promoting the forest conservation agenda, which has become an increasingly central priority for the country, both domestically and diplomatically.

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The Igarapé Institute is an independent think-and-do tank that conducts research, develops solutions, and establishes partnerships to influence public and corporate policies and practices, addressing key challenges related to nature, climate, and security in Brazil and worldwide. Igarapé is a nonprofit, nonpartisan organization based in Rio de Janeiro, operating at both local and global levels.

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